

Value of Acute-Phase Proteins in the URS Surgery and Complications

Deniz İpek, MD

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Original Research Article

Value of Acute-Phase Proteins in the URS Surgery and Complications

Running Title: *Acute Phase Protein Levels in URS Surgery*

ABSTRACT

Background: URS and ESWL are the most preferred first-line treatment options in cases where the stone needs to be removed. URS is recommended as priority to patients who want to get rid of stones quickly with a single treatment application.

Aim: In this study we tried to elucidate the preoperative and postoperative haematological, biochemical and acute phase protein changes in patients who underwent ureteroscopy and its complications.

Materials & Method: A total of 115 patients who have been operated via URS due to kidney stones in our institution between 2019 and 2021 and patients who underwent ESWL as a control group were included in this study. Hemogram, blood biochemistry, C-Reactive Protein, Haptoglobin, transferrin values were analyzed in all patients before and at 1,3 and 30 days after surgery. The acute phase protein changes in case of complications in 15 patients who developed complications in URS surgery were analyzed.

Results: A statistically significant difference was observed in Bk, BUN, Cr, Na, CRP, HPT and TRF and Bk, Na, and Ca values measured in the first month ($p < 0.05$). The development of complications were 8 times more common if the stone was located on the left side. One-unit decrease in Cl reduced complication rate 0.6-fold decrease in the pre-operative period and 0.8-fold on the first day. One-unit decrease in TRF reduced complication rate 0.7-fold decrease in the pre-operative period and 0.02-fold on the third day. The CRP cut-off value of 63.95, HPT cut-off value of over 5.84 and TRF cut-off value of below 2.04 increased complication rate.

Conclusion: Regarding the results of this study one can say that acute phase reactants can be utilized as convenient predictive biomarkers of complications in patients who underwent

ureteroscopy. As far as we know this was the first study to elaborate their importance in the literature.

Keywords: *Ureteroscopy, complication, Extracorporeal Shock Wave Lithotripsy, CRP, HPT, transferrin*

Abbreviations:

APP: *acute phase proteins*

ASA: *American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification system*

BUN: *blood urea nitrogen*

CI: *confidence interval*

CRP: *C Reactive protein*

CT: *computerized tomography*

EAU: *European Association of Urology*

ESWL: *Extracorporeal Shock Wave Lithotripsy*

HPT: *haptoglobin*

ICU: *Intensive Care Unit*

KUB films: *kidney, ureter, bladder films*

OR: *odds ratio*

PNL: *Percutaneous nephrolithotomy*

RIRC: *retrograde intrarenal surgery*

ROC: *Receiver Operating Characteristics*

SD: *standard deviation*

SIRS: *Systemic inflammatory response syndrome*

SPSS: *Statistical Package for the Social Sciences*

TRF: *transferrin*

URS: *Ureteroscopy*

UTI: *urinary tract infections*

Introduction

URS (*ureteroscopy*) treatment has been initially accepted as an alternative to ESWL in the treatment ureteral stones and small kidney stones (1, 2). Today, there are studies showing that URS is even superior to ESWL (*Extracorporeal Shock Wave Lithotripsy*) and PNL (*percutaneous nephrolithotomy*) even in the large kidney stones (3).

Recent innovations in the design and durability of endoscopes over the past years has revolutionized the utilization of URS. Today, the caliber of rigid URSs has been reduced to <7.5F, therefore, ureteral orifice dilatation is not required in most cases. Fully rigid URSs that are difficult to move in the ureter in years, but softer, stretchable, semi-rigid and flexible URSs have been produced (4).

URS and ESWL are the most preferred first-line treatment options in cases where the stone needs to be removed (5). The big dilemma is the decision of URS or ESWL in treatment of ureteral stones. At this stage patient selection is also important. While URS is recommended as priority to patients who want to get rid of stones quickly with a single treatment application, ESWL can be performed in patients who do not want to be hospitalized and receive anesthesia. In the treatment of ureteral stones that do not pass spontaneously; location of the stone, its size, non-opaque or settled, degree of obstruction, renal functions and proximal dilatation of the stone play an important role in determining the treatment modality (5).

The American and the European Urology Society (*AUA and EAU*) guidelines recommended ESWL and URS as first-line treatment in healthy, non-pregnant patients with normal contralateral kidney function and stones smaller than 20 mm in unilateral ureter who do not have a second stone requiring treatment (5, 6).

Non-invasive approach should be considered in the first place in ureteral stones smaller than 10 mm. The stone should be followed closely in case of distal progression of the stone or formation of hydronephrosis. In the presence of ongoing obstruction, non-advancing stones, increasing or persistent renal colic, the stone should be removed. It has been emphasized that ESWL or URS approach is the first treatment option for ureteral stones larger than 10 mm in size. In addition, while URS is recommended primarily for distal ureteral stones >10 mm, ESWL is recommended primarily for proximal ureteral stones <10 mm (6).

Preoperative and postoperative acute phase proteins are both inexpensive and noninvasive measure CRP is the major determinant of these inflammatory markers. CRP, a protein synthesized from the liver in inflammatory reactions, is used for the recognition and elimination of pathogens, clearance of necrotic and apoptotic cells. It is synthesized in the body within 4 – 6 hours and doubles within 8 hours. It takes about 1 week to return to normal values in the blood following the inflammatory processes. It can increase 15-40 times in invasive bacterial infections, 3-5 times in viral infections, and more than 10 times in influenza or CMV infections (7).

Ferritin is stimulated by infection and infectious situation could mislead higher iron storage than it truly exists in case referring to the concentration of plasma ferritin. Ferritin can increase 1000 times rapidly due to its short half-life, while transferrin levels decrease depending on the severity. Regarding this, ferritin can be measured to determine response to infectious and non-infectious inflammation and monitor to evaluate the success of treatment interventions (8, 9).

Haptoglobin, a protein which transports hemoglobin, becomes elevated during an acute-phase reaction and decrease in hemolytic conditions and severe hepatocellular deficiency (7).

Study Hypothesis

In this study we tried to elucidate the preoperative and postoperative haematological, biochemical, and acute phase protein changes in patients who underwent ureteroscopy due to kidney stones and compared them with patients who underwent ESWL treatment.

This study has also aimed to determine the change of APP proteins and threshold values in patients with developing complications.

Materials & Method

A total of 115 patients who have been operated via ureteroscopy due to kidney stones in our institution between 2019 and 2021 and patients who underwent ESWL as a control group were included in this study. The ethics committee approval has been granted at 01.04.2021 and protocol number: 2021/36. Informed consent has been obtained from all participants.

Inclusion Criteria

Individuals who were aged between 18 to 60 years and ASA classes I and II have been enrolled in the analysis.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with liver dysfunction and abnormal blood coagulation were not included in the study. Patients with a history of cancer and/or immune diseases were also excluded.

Subjects who had positive culture before the surgery has been treated and included in the study after negative culture result.

Hemogram, blood biochemistry, C-Reactive Protein, Haptoglobin, transferrin values were analyzed in all patients before and at 1,3 and 30 days after surgery. We tried to determine the factors affecting the complication and the threshold value of acute phase protein change in case of complications in 15 patients who developed complications in URS surgery.

RIRC Technique

All stages of the procedure has been performed on the endourology table, with the patient in the lithotomy position, under C-arm fluoroscopy control. Before all procedures, the ureter on the calculus side was checked with URS to control unexpected pathologies and to facilitate access sheath placement. Any stenosis from the ureteral orifice to the ureteropelvic junction was widened with balloon dilatation. Access sheath was placed in all cases. All attempts were performed using 7.5F fiberoptic (*Storz FLEX-X2, Tuttlingen, Germany*) and a 200 or 273-lm laser fiber. Holmium YAG laser was used as the energy source.

At the end of laser lithotripsy fragments smaller than 2 mm were left to fall off spontaneously, fragments larger than 2 mm were taken with a basket. To confirm the success of the operation, a systematic review of the collector system was carried out at the end of the operation. A 4.8F DJ stent was routinely placed for each patient and removed 3 to 4 weeks after the procedure.

Operation time was calculated based on the time from access sheath insertion to DJ stent placement. Postoperative stone-free rates were determined based on DUSGs taken at discharge and at the 4th week postoperatively.

ESWL was performed as an outpatient procedure using an electrohydraulic extracorporeal lithotripter. Intra-muscular non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medication was administered prior to the procedure, and The procedure was concluded after seeing

fragmentation on fluoroscopy or after a maximum of 3000 shock waves. Patients without clearance after three sessions were referred for other modalities or follow-up. Additional sessions were not scheduled earlier than 15 days. ESWL patients were followed after the first session. The second session has been performed after follow up period of first month.

Postoperative complications were stratified according to the modified Clavien classification system. Vital signs were closely monitored, and abdominal plain film examinations were rescheduled the next morning. Culture-specific antibiotics treatment and antibiotic treatment continued until ureteroscopy. A stone-free status was regarded as nodetectable stones on KUB films 1 month after ureteroscopy. Additionally, NCCT would likely be required if KUB showed any signs of high density. Fragments less than 4mm were also considered as not meaningful stones when determining stone clearance.

Modified Clavien Classification System (17)

Grade I: Any deviation from the normal postoperative course without the need for pharmacological treatment or surgical, endoscopic, and radiological interventions. Allowed therapeutic regimens are: antiemetics, antipyretics, analgesics, diuretics, electrolytes, and physiotherapy.

Grade II: Requiring pharmacological treatment with drugs other than such allowed for grade I complications.

Grade IIIa: Requiring surgical, endoscopic, or radiological interventions not under general anaesthesia.

Grade IIIb: Requiring surgical, endoscopic, or radiological interventions under general anaesthesia.

Grade IVa: Life-threatening complication requiring ICU management (single organ dysfunction).

Grade IVb: Life-threatening complication requiring ICU management (multiple organ dysfunction).

Grade V: Death

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was performed in SPSS for Windows 23.0 package program. Frequency and percentage were given for categorical data, and median, minimum and maximum descriptive values for continuous data. Categorical variables were evaluated with the Chi-square test. Evaluation of the difference between groups was done with the Kruskal Wallis Test. The effects of risk factors, which were thought to have a significant effect on the development of complications as a result of univariate statistical analyzes, were investigated with Logistic Regression analysis. Odds Ratio, 95% confidence interval for each risk factor was calculated. Calculation of breakpoints for complication development was evaluated by ROC analysis. The results were considered statistically significant when the p value was less than 0.05.

Results

Within the scope of the study, three different groups with kidney stone treatment were evaluated. The first group was the flexible ureteroscopy patients with no complications, the second group was the flexible ureteroscopy patients who developed complications, and the third group was the ESWL patients. The distribution of demographic and clinical findings of the treatment groups were given in *Table 1*. When the table was examined, the location and size of the stone, Hg, BUN, Ca, Cl, TRF values measured on the first day and additionally, Hg, Bk, BUN, Cr, Na, Cl, CRP, HPT and TRF were measured on the third day. A statistically significant difference was observed in Bk, BUN, Cr, Na, CRP, HPT and TRF and Bk, Na, and Ca values measured in the first month ($p < 0.05$).

The distribution of risk factors affecting the development of complications in patients who developed complications after the flexible ureteroscopy was given in *Table 2*. When the table was examined, it was determined that the development of complications were 8 times more common if the stone was located on the left side. Similarly, one-unit change in the size of the stone caused 1.003-fold in the rate of complications.

One-unit increase in Bk value on the first day increased complication rate by 2-fold and one-unit increase in Bk value on the third day increased complication rate 7 times, and a one-unit increase in Bk value in the first month caused increased complication rate 4-fold. One unit increase in BUN increased complication rate 1.5 times on the first day and 1.3 times on the third day. One unit increase in Cr value increased complication rate by 2.2 fold on the first day and 2.7 on the third day. Finally, one unit increase in Na value increased complication rate by 1.6. A one-unit increase in HPT increased complication rate by 8.9 fold in the pre-operative period 7 fold in the first day and 8 fold in the third day

One-unit decrease in Cl reduced complication rate 0.6-fold decrease in the pre-operative period and 0.8-fold on the first day. One-unit decrease in TRF reduced complication rate 0.7-fold decrease in the pre-operative period and 0.02-fold on the third day.

As a result of the ROC analysis, the development of complications and cut-off value relationship with several parameters have been investigated. It was observed that CRP cut-off value of 63.95, HPT cut-off value of over 5.84 and TRF cut-off value of below 2.04 increased complication rate.

Discussion

Different treatment options are recommended for the treatment of ureteral stones. These include ESWL, flexible or rigid ureteroscopy, and open or laparoscopic ureterolithotomy. High success rates are reported for ESWL and ureteroscopic interventions, which are the two most preferred methods today. While ureteroscopic interventions are recommended for patients who want to be cleared of the stone quickly with a single treatment attempt, who do not want to experience the process required to reduce the stone fragments and the pain and additional invasive procedures that may be experienced in this process; ESWL treatment is given priority for patients who do not want to be hospitalized or who do not want to receive anesthesia (10).

European Association of Urology (*EAU*) guidelines clearly emphasize that a decision should be made on the basis of stone size, stone location, adequacy of equipment and patient selection, regarding which method should be chosen when treating ureteral stones (*11*). Based on the size and location of the stone, stone-free rates are reported to be higher than ESWL when lower, middle ureter and upper ureteral stones larger than 10 mm are treated with URS (*11*). Strohmaier et al. considered the preferences of patients with ureteral stones and stated that 66.4% of the patients preferred ESWL as the first treatment option (*12*). Peschel et al. found that satisfaction was higher in patients treated with ureteroscopic interventions (*13*).

URS is an invasive procedure and several complications such as: retraction of the stone, bleeding, mucosal injury, perforation, rupture, ureter avulsion may occur. Although stenting is a common practice after URS, there are publications reporting that routine application is unnecessary (*14*). Stent placement is recommended in patients with mucosal edema or damage, bleeding, ureteral rupture, single kidney or stone migration. Bacteremia and increased morbidity rates have been reported after ESWL treatment in ureteral stones accompanied by urinary infection. These patients should primarily be offered ureteroscopic interventions (*15*).

Calcium oxalate monohydrate, cystine and brushite stones are resistant to ESWL. The number of shock waves should be increased in the treatment of these stones. Another problematic group in ESWL treatment is non-opaque stones. ESWL treatment is possible by determining the location of the stone in the ureter by administering intravenous contrast material (*14, 15*). In our study, it has been determined that the development of complications was 8 times more common if the stone was located on the left side. Similarly, one-unit change in the size of the stone caused 1.003-fold in the rate of complications.

Today, ureteroscopic interventions are preferred in the first place in the approach to lower and middle ureteral stones. ESWL is the more preferred method for upper ureteral stones that are more difficult to reach (*15*). With the use of small diameter semi-rigid and flexible ureteroscopes and Holmium-YAG laser, URS has become a treatment option with

high efficacy and safety and low complication rate in all locations. However, this treatment is still applied with rigid ureteroscopes in many clinics due to its high cost (16).

Although the total stone-free rate varies according to the location of the stone, it has been reported between 81% and 94% in a single session (17). The success rate of flexible URS was further increased with the use of tools to prevent stone escaping in upper ureteral region, with an overall success rate of 81% (93% for stones < 10 mm, 87% for stones > 10 mm). On the other hand, it has been reported that the stone-free rates revealed by flexible URS are higher than semi-rigid URS (87% and 77%, respectively) (18).

Park et al. prospectively evaluated the results of 160 patients who underwent URS (95 cases) or ESWL (65 cases) with the diagnosis of ureteral stones (4 – 15 mm). Stone-free rates were 93% in the ESWL group at the end of the third session and 100% in the URS group (19).

Acute-phase reactants can be elaborated as a group of liver originated proteins that has been synthesized in response to several inflammatory and infectious situations. Their secretion can be induced via cytokines, growth factors, anaphylatoxins, glucocorticoids and catecholamines. The response of these acute phase proteins can be both increase and decrease of plasma levels. Reduced albumin and transferrin (TRF) levels are observed while CRP, haptoglobin, fibrinogen and others increase. The role of these mediators can be explained as ameliorating tissue damage, regeneration and neutralizing inflammation (20).

CRP is often perceived as a non-specific acute phase reactant as it is elevated in diseases like rheumatoid arthritis, cardiovascular disease, vascular diseases and sometimes may not be elevated in several inflammatory diseases such as scleroderma, ulcerative colitis and SLE. Additionally, CRP levels are strongly associated with the patient's age and immunological status. In this study we have found statistically significant CRP increase in the first and third day of pre-operative period and first and third day of postoperative period (21). In this study we have observed a statistically significant difference CRP, values measured in the first month ($p < 0.05$).

In case of infection and/or inflammation, haptoglobin, increases simultaneously and forms a complex with hemoglobin as a positive acute phase reactant. It also decreases in hemolytic conditions and severe hepatocellular deficiency (22). In this study we have observed a statistically significant difference HPT values measured in the first month ($p < 0.05$).

Ferritin is also another acute phase reactant and it is elevated in inflammation with other mediators like CRP and ESR. During inflammation and/or infection iron is not released to transferrin (*TRF*) and transferrin-bound iron, is low despite a normal or elevated ferritin (22). It was observed that CRP cut-off value of 63.95, HPT cut-off value of over 5.84 and TRF cut-off value of below 2.04 increased complication rate.

Conclusion

Regarding the results of this study one can say that acute phase reactants can be utilized as convenient predictive biomarkers of complications in patients who underwent ureteroscopy. As far as we know this was the first study to elaborate their importance in the literature.

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Table 1. Analysis of Demographic and Laboratory Parameters by Groups

Characteristics (N=115)	FURS AFP (n=50)	FURS AFP Komp. (n=15)	ESWL (n=50)	p value	Delta *
	Median (Min-Max) or n (%)	Median (Min-Max) or n (%)	Median (Min-Max) or n (%)		
Age, years	47 (17-81)	48 (25-64)	45 (15-80)	0.733	
Gender					
Male	29 (58.0)	10 (66.7)	26 (52.0)	0.580	
Female	21 (42.0)	5 (33.3)	24 (48.0)		
Side					
Right	28 (56.0)	2 (13.3)	22 (44.0)	0.014	
Left	22 (44.0)	13 (86.7)	28 (56.0)		
Stone Localisation					
Kidney Upper Poles	13 (26.0)	1 (6.7)	3 (6.0)	<0.0001	
Kidney Middle Pol	8 (16.0)	6 (40.0)	18 (36.0)		
Kidney Renal Pelvis	19 (38.0)	5 (33.3)	15 (30.0)		
Kidney Lower Poles	10 (20.0)	3 (20.0)	2 (4.0)		
Ureter Upper End	-	-	8 (16.0)		
Ureter Middle	-	-	4 (8.0)		
Stone size (mm²)	476.1 (125.6-1265.4)	642.3 (156.5-1245.2)	130.6 (39.8-1178.5)	<0.0001	a-c/b-c
Pre-op Hg	11.7 (10.1-17.3)	12.9 (11.4-15.6)	11.8 (9.8-16.8)	0.040	a-b
P1 Hg	11.7 (9.9-17.4)	12.4 (7.5-16.9)	11.5 (9.9-16.8)	0.724	
P3 Hg	12.2 (10.1-16.8)	12.5 (9.6-15.3)	11.6 (9.9-17.0)	0.487	
P30 Hg	12.2 (10.2-17.7)	12.3 (11.5-14.9)	12.7 (10.2-17.4)	0.529	
Pre-op Bk	8.3 (5.2-10.4)	8.5 (5.9-10.2)	8.4 (5.2-10.4)	0.746	
P1 Bk	13.5 (9.6-16.8)	17.6 (9.6-21.4)	7.5 (5.5-11.2)	<0.0001	a-b-c
P3 Bk	8.1 (5.5-11.3)	14.2 (9.2-20.1)	7.4 (5.5-9.9)	<0.0001	a-b/b-c
P30 Bk	7.8 (5.6-11.2)	10.8 (6.7-13.5)	8.0 (5.2-10.4)	<0.0001	a-b/b-c
Pre-op Trb	243.5 (156-368)	258 (213-325)	254 (156-368)	0.706	
P1 Trb	252 (158-369)	252 (90-324)	253.5 (154-369)	0.829	
P3 Trb	247 (157-367)	278 (135-367)	249 (157-367)	0.789	
P30 Trb	255 (177-366)	254 (177-326)	255 (151-366)	0.904	
Pre-op Osm	300.5 (289-307)	298 (290-305)	301 (283-307)	0.450	
P1 Osm	301 (289-308)	303 (283-323)	301 (283-307)	0.304	
P3 Osm	301 (293-306)	301 (291-309)	300.5 (289-310)	0.603	
P30 Osm	301 (289-308)	302 (297-327)	301 (289-334)	0.332	
Pre-op Bun	13 (7-29)	14 (8-22)	16 (7-35)	0.027	a-c
P1 Bun	12 (7-29)	35 (23-92)	16 (10-30)	<0.0001	a-b-c

P3 Bun	15 (7-27)	25 (12-54)	11.5 (7-29)	<0.0001	a-b/b-c
P30 Bun	13 (8-25)	15 (9-26)	14.5 (8-27)	0.304	
Pre-Op Cr	0.8 (0.4-1.8)	0.8 (0.6-9.0)	0.8 (0,4-9,0)	0.945	
P1 Cr	0.8 (0.5-1.7)	1.5 (1.0-2.5)	0.8 (0,5-1,7)	<0.0001	a-b
P3 Cr	0.8 (0.5-1.2)	0.9 (0.7-2.1)	0.8 (0,5-1,2)	0.014	a-b
P30 Cr	0.8 (0.6-1.1)	0.8 (0.5-1.5)	0.8 (0,4-1,5)	0.969	
Pre-op Na	142 (140-149)	142 (140-146)	144 (140-149)	0.294	
P1 Na	143.5 (140-149)	146 (140-149)	142 (140-148)	<0.0001	a-b/b-c
P3 Na	144 (139-149)	144 (140-149)	143 (140-147)	0.261	
P30 Na	142 (139-149)	144 (141-147)	144 (139-149)	0.005	a-c

Table 1. Continued

Characteristics (N=115)	FURS AFP (n=50)	FURS AFP Komp. (n=15)	FURS AFP ESWL (n=50)	p value	Delta *
	Median (Min-Max) or n (%)	Median (Min-Max) or n (%)	Median (Min-Max) or n (%)		
Pre-op K	4.3 (3.5-5.3)	4.3 (3.8-5.0)	4.2 (3.8-5.0)	0.690	
P1 K	4.1 (3.2-4.8)	4.2 (3.9-4.6)	4.2 (3.7-5.1)	0.076	
P3 K	4.2 (3.2-5.4)	4.2 (3.8-5.2)	4.1 (3.2-5.3)	0.190	
P30 K	4.3 (3.3-5.3)	4.3 (3.5-5.3)	4.3 (3.2-5.4)	0.850	
Pre-op Ca	9.4 (8.4-10.4)	9.8 (9.0-10.3)	9.8 (8.9-10.9)	<0.0001	a-b/a-c
P1 Ca	9.5 (8.4-10.7)	9.8 (7.5-10.4)	9.6 (8.4-10.9)	0.512	
P3 Ca	9.6 (8.4-10.7)	9.5 (8.5-10.7)	9.6 (8.4-10.7)	0.915	
P30 Ca	9.6 (8.4-10.9)	9.8 (8.5-10.7)	9.8 (8.9-10.8)	0.043	a-c
Pre-op Cl	107 (100-123)	103 (96-106)	109 (103-115)	<0.0001	a-b/b-c
P1 Cl	108 (102-116)	105 (99-121)	108.5 (101-118)	0.020	a-b/b-c
P3 Cl	109 (102-118)	107 (101-115)	107 (100-123)	0.331	
P30 Cl	108 (101-118)	106 (99.0-114)	108 (102-116)	0.152	
Pre-op CRP	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	1.000	
P1 CRP	42.7 (19.2-58.2)	88.9 (69.7-102.8)	5.7 (3.1-9.9)	<0.0001	a-b-c
P3 CRP	19.4 (6.1-43.3)	62.4 (42.4-73.9)	4.3 (3.1-8.1)	<0.0001	a-b-c
P30 CRP	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	1.000	
Pre-Op HPT	1.38 (0.46-2.08)	1.62 (1.17-2.63)	1.33 (0.46-1.87)	0.062	
P1 HPT	5.25 (4.01-6.65)	6.99 (5.45-9.84)	1.36 (0.23-1.87)	<0.0001	a-b-c
P3 HPT	2.97 (2.02-4.23)	4.22 (2.59-7.42)	1.33 (0.13-1.97)	<0.0001	a-b-c
P30 HPT	1.51 (0.38-1.97)	1.84 (0.92-2.66)	1.37 (0.22-10.258)	0.058	
Pre-op TRF	2.25 (1.93-3.40)	2.56 (2.11-3.40)	2.56 (2.02-3.68)	0.009	a-c
P1 TRF	2.33 (1.91-3.40)	1.79 (0.90-2.42)	2.35 (2.01-3.16)	<0.0001	a-b/b-c
P3 TRF	2.37 (1.83-3.23)	1.94 (1.12-2.95)	2.64 (2.09-3.25)	<0.0001	a-b-c
P30 TRF	2.43 (1.91-3.40)	2.21 (1.94-3.16)	2.57 (1.97-3.68)	0.061	

* a = FURS AFP, b = FURS AFP Comp., c = FURS AFP ESWL.

Table 2. Analysis of Factors Affecting the Development of FURS AFP Complications

Characteristics (N=65)	FURS AFP (n=50)	FURS AFP Complications (n=15)	p value	OR (95% CI)
	Median (Min-Max) or n (%)	Median (Min-Max) or n (%)		
Age, years	47 (17-81)	48 (25-64)	0.487	0.985 (0.944-1.028)
Gender				
Male	29 (58.0)	10 (66.7)	-	1.000 ^a
Female	21 (42.0)	5 (33.3)	0.549	0.690 (0.206-2.319)
Side				
Right	28 (56.0)	2 (13.3)	-	1.000^a
Left	22 (44.0)	13 (86.7)	0.009	8.273 (1.687-40.567)
Laser Frequecy	6 (6-12)	6 (6-10)	0.265	0.765 (0.477-1.226)
Laser Energy	3500 (1500-3500)	3000 (1500-3500)	0.824	1.000 (0.999-1.001)
Total Energy	21 (12-21)	20 (12-21)	0.107	0.855 (0.706-1.035)
Ans Time	84 (50-124)	87 (62-120)	0.282	1.025 (0.980-1.071)
Operasyon Süresi	70 (40-100)	75 (46-100)	0.238	1.029 (0.981-1.080)
Rez. Stone	6 (12.0)	4 (26.7)	0.178	2.667 (0.640-11.113)
Mai Mik	6 (4-10)	6 (4-12)	0.066	1.426 (0.977-2.081)
Stone Size (mm ²)	476.1 (125.6-1265.4)	642.3 (156,5-1245.2)	0.001	1.003 (1.001-1.005)
Pre-op Hg	11.7 (10.1-17.3)	12.9 (11.4-15.6)	0.071	1.301 (0.977-1.731)
P1 Hg	11.7 (9.9-17.4)	12.4 (7.5-16.9)	0.942	0.990 (0.744-1.316)
P3 Hg	12.2 (10.1-16.8)	12.5 (9.6-15.3)	0.979	1.004 (0.729-1.384)
P30 Hg	12.2 (10.2-17.7)	12.3 (11.5-14.9)	0.833	1.036 (0.744-1.445)
Pre-op Bk	8.3 (5.2-10.4)	8.5 (5.9-10.2)	0.566	1.127 (0.749-1.695)
P1 Bk	13.5 (9.6-16.8)	17.6 (9.6-21.4)	<0.0001	1.966 (1.419-2.724)
P3 Bk	8.1 (5.5-11.3)	14.2 (9.2-20.1)	0.003	6.963 (1.939-25.004)
P30 Bk	7.8 (5.6-11.2)	10.8 (6.7-13.5)	<0.0001	3.620 (2.080-6.302)
Pre-op Trb	243.5 (156-368)	258 (213-325)	0.635	1.003 (0.992-1.014)
P1 Trb	252 (158-369)	252 (90-324)	0.291	0.995 (0.984-1.005)

P3 Trb	247 (157-367)	278 (135-367)	0.607	1.003 (0.991-1.015)
P30 Trb	255 (177-366)	254 (177-326)	0.844	1.001 (0.989-1.013)
Pre-op Osm	300.5 (289-307)	298 (290-305)	0.246	0.927 (0.815-1.054)
P1 Osm	301 (289-308)	303 (283-323)	0.145	1.100 (0.968-1.249)
P3 Osm	301 (293-306)	301 (291-309)	0.558	0.962 (0.844-1.096)
P30 Osm	301 (289-308)	302 (297-327)	0.083	1.056 (0.993-1.122)
Pre-op Bun	13 (7-29)	14 (8-22)	0.677	0.978 (0.881-1.086)
P1 Bun	12 (7-29)	35 (23-92)	<0.0001	1.538 (1.224-1.931)
P3 Bun	15 (7-27)	25 (12-54)	<0.0001	1.294 (1.145-1.463)
P30 Bun	13 (8-25)	15 (9-26)	0.186	1.079 (0.964-1.207)
Pre-Op Cr	0.8 (0.4-1.8)	0,8 (0.6-9.0)	0.198	1.253 (0.889-1.767)
P1 Cr	0.8 (0.5-1.7)	1.5 (1.0-2.5)	<0.0001	2.223 (0.685-7.212)
P3 Cr	0.8 (0.5-1.2)	0.9 (0.7-2.1)	0.001	2.714 (0.969-7.602)
P30 Cr	0.8 (0.6-1.1)	0.8 (0.5-1.5)	0.262	4.326 (0.334-56.020)
Pre-op Na	142 (140-149)	142 (140-146)	0.319	0.878 (0.680-1.134)
P1 Na	143.5 (140-149)	146 (140-149)	<0.0001	1.634 (1.247-2.140)
P3 Na	144 (139-149)	144 (140-149)	0.316	1.134 (0.887-1.448)
P30 Na	142 (139-149)	144 (141-147)	0.508	1.080 (0.860-1.356)

OR: Odds Ratio, CI: Confidence Interval, a: Reference Category

Table 2. Continued

Characteristics (N=65)	FURS AFP (n=50)	FURS AFP Complications (n=15)	p value	OR (95% CI)
	Median (Min-Max) or n (%)	Median (Min-Max) or n (%)		
Pre-op K	4.3 (3.5-5.3)	4.3 (3.8-5.0)	0.280	2.538 (0.468-13.773)
P1 K	4.1 (3.2-4.8)	4.2 (3.9-4.6)	0.589	1.637 (0.274-9.796)
P3 K	4.2 (3.2-5.4)	4.2 (3.8-5.2)	0.605	1.409 (0.383-5.179)
P30 K	4.3 (3.3-5.3)	4.3 (3.5-5.3)	0.888	0.913 (0.256-3.258)
Pre-op Ca	9.4 (8.4-10.4)	9.8 (9.0-10.3)	0.119	2.559 (0.785-8.340)
P1 Ca	9.5 (8.4-10.7)	9.8 (7.5-10.4)	0.867	1.078 (0.447-2.598)
P3 Ca	9.6 (8.4-10.7)	9.5 (8.5-10.7)	0.792	0.875 (0.326-2.351)
P30 Ca	9.6 (8.4-10.9)	9.8 (8.5-10.7)	0.839	1.118 (0.380-3.291)
Pre-op Cl	107 (100-123)	103 (96-106)	<0.0001	0.601 (0.468-0.771)
P1 Cl	108 (102-116)	105 (99-121)	0.014	0.818 (0.697-0.959)
P3 Cl	109 (102-118)	107 (101-115)	0.313	0.933 (0.815-1.068)
P30 Cl	108 (101-118)	106 (99.0-114)	0.079	0.870 (0.744-1.016)
Pre-op CRP	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	-	-
P1 CRP	42.7 (19.2-58.2)	88.9 (69.7-102.8)	0.987	1.795 (0.500-3.127)
P3 CRP	19.4 (6.1-43.3)	62.4 (42.4-73.9)	0.352	1.894 (0.493-7.278)
P30 CRP	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	3.1 (3.1-3.1)	-	-
Pre-Op HPT	1.38 (0.46-2.08)	1.62 (1.17-2.63)	0.008	8.901 (1.773-44.676)
P1 HPT	5.25 (4.01-6.65)	6.99 (5.45-9.84)	0.001	6.988 (5.652-7.004)
P3 HPT	2.97 (2.02-4.23)	4.22 (2.59-7.42)	<0.0001	8.161 (2.795-23.832)

P30 HPT	1.51 (0.38-1.97)	1.84 (0.92-2.66)	0.373	1.214 (0.793-1.858)
Pre-op TRF	2.25 (1.93-3.40)	2.56 (2.11-3.40)	0.084	3.558 (0.841-15.050)
P1 TRF	2.33 (1.91-3.40)	1.79 (0.90-2.42)	0.003	0.762 (0.069-1.123)
P3 TRF	2.37 (1.83-3.23)	1.94 (1.12-2.95)	0.001	0.017 (0.001-0.211)
P30 TRF	2.43 (1.91-3.40)	2.21 (1.94-3.16)	0.768	0.796 (0.175-3.621)

OR: Odds Ratio, CI: Confidence Interval, a: Reference Category

Table 3. ROC analysis for CRP, HPT, and TRF on the Post-Operative First Day of Complication Development

Risk Factors	AUC (95% CI)	Cut-off	p	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)
CRP	1.000 (1.000-1.000)	63.95	<0.0001	100.0	100.0
HPT	0.976 (0.931-1.000)	5.84	<0.0001	93.3	92.0
TRF	0.925 (0.830-1.000)	2.04	<0.0001	86.7	86.0

